

Research Data Management Training

An implementation project for the Institutional
Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

Victoria University

February 2023

About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The aim of this project was to implement an online research data management (RDM) training module for Victoria University researchers and HDR students.

A project steering group to oversee and provide direction was established. The steering group comprised senior representatives from across the institution: ITS, Library, Research Services, Office of Training, Quality and Integrity, and Graduate Research.

There were several stages to the project.

1. An audit was conducted of research data management (RDM) support, training and guidance currently offered at VU. Stakeholders were consulted on current practices and needs around RDM.
2. Identification and selection of a training resource suitable for adapting to the VU environment. Criteria for selection included: meeting minimum competencies listed in the Institutional Underpinnings (IU) element, a software format that could be applied with existing VU learning systems, and a licence that allowed sharing. The resource selected was an online Research Data Management training module developed by Macquarie University.
3. Customisation of the Macquarie resource with VU specific content. Obtaining feedback on the training resource with a representative sample of researchers.

The [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Support, Training and Guidance element was used at several times during the project. The definitions of support, training and guidance helped locate and identify existing resources during the audit phase of the project. The minimum required competencies for researchers was used as a baseline for developing the training. The recommendation to repurpose existing resources determined the overall strategy for developing the training resource.

Resulting Improvements

The establishment of the project steering group and conducting an audit resulted in greater understanding of the support, training and guidance provided at VU, along with where gaps existed. The online training module provides an easily accessible resource that covers minimum (plus some desired) researcher competencies.

Next Steps

The training module is being loaded into VU's online staff development system (VU Develop). Inclusion in this system enables tracking of completion rates as well as ensuring a regular review process is implemented. Senior decision makers are considering the option of making the course mandatory for

some cohorts (e.g. higher degree research students at candidature) and/or integrating within the higher degree research coursework.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

- A public version comprising the training SCORM files is available for downloading from the VU Research Repository [Research Data Management Online | VU Research Repository | Victoria University | Melbourne Australia](#)
- A public facing course is also being considered via a Learning Management System. Access will be via a simple email registration process
- Results of the Audit, conducted at the beginning of the project, have been published in the [VU Research Repository](#)
- The training is to be included in the staff development online system, accessed by VU staff and HDR students.

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).